

Qualification Survey

Introduction

Hi,

We're researching how students use the in-IDE learning format within the JetBrains Academy plugin to learn coding. For example, we would like to find out what plugin features students tend to use as they take a course and what helps them solve the coding tasks when they get stuck.

If you are interested in taking part in our study, please fill out the form below. If your background meets our research criteria, we will contact you to arrange a video call. The anonymized results of the study will be used for research purposes.

As a token of our appreciation, you will receive a \$150 Amazon Gift Card after the call.

Completing the form should take no more than 5 minutes. All information you provide will be kept confidential.

Let's get started!

* Indicates a required question

Have you ever used the in-IDE learning within the JetBrains Academy plugin to learn programming languages? *

- Yes
- No

How long have you been using the JetBrains Academy plugin to learn programming languages? *

- I just started
- A couple of weeks
- 1-2 months
- Other, please specify:

What is your age range? *

- 17 or younger

- 18–20
- 21–29
- 30–39
- 40–49
- 50–59
- 60 or older

What is your country or region of current residence? *

- Countries list

What is your current occupation? *

- Student
- Working student
- Freelancer
- Fully employed by a company or organization
- Partially employed by a company or organization
- Retired
- Unemployed
- Other, please specify:

How did you study computer science? *

- Online via a MOOC
- Online in a bootcamp
- Online by using YouTube guides
- Offline in university
- Offline in high school
- Other, please specify:
- I have never studied computer science

Have you studied computer science in university? *

- Yes, I majored or am majoring in computer science
- Yes, I studied or am studying computer science but not as my major
- No, I didn't study computer science in university

Which programming languages do you use on a regular basis? *

- Java
- C
- C++
- Python
- C#
- PHP
- JavaScript
- Ruby
- Kotlin
- Swift
- Objective-C
- Scala
- Go
- SQL (PL/SQL, T-SQL, or other programming extensions of SQL)
- Rust
- Haskell
- HTML / CSS
- Crystal
- Visual Basic
- R
- TypeScript
- Dart
- CoffeeScript
- Clojure / ClojureScript
- Delphi
- COBOL
- Groovy
- Ceylon
- Perl
- Assembly
- MATLAB
- Shell scripting languages (bash/shell/PowerShell)
- Julia
- F#
- Other, please specify:
- I don't use any programming languages

Please share your GitHub profile (or any links to your projects):

- [Open question]

Please provide your contact details:

- First name:
- Email address: